

FOREST4EU

Connecting forestry and agroforestry partnerships across Europe

Centar kompetencija d.o.o.
za istraživanje i razvoj

Funded by
the European Union

Funded by the European Union (Grant n. 101086216). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or REA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Operational Group (OG)

OG IR_MP3 Latvia

OG funding

Index

1. WOODL: Software for mobilisation and efficient use of resources involved in transportation of timber from forest to destination location .	4
1.1 Objective.....	4
1.2 Logistics WEB software requirements:	5
1.3 Working with the website.....	5
1.3.1 Logging in.....	5
1.3.2 Description of each section of the interface.....	6
1.3.3 Point icons and text colour explanations.....	12
1.3.4 Coordinates correction.....	12
1.3.5 Working with data and filters.....	13
1.3.6 Forest clearings.....	14
1.3.7 Circulation filtering by wood templates	15
1.3.8 Filtering of felling by felling status	16
1.3.9 Viewing the felling data	17
1.3.10 List of felling sites	18
1.3.11. Establishing or repairing a new clearing	19
1.3.12 Establishment of a new stacking yard	20

1. WOODL: Software for mobilisation and efficient use of resources involved in transportation of timber from forest to destination location

1.1 Objective

The purpose of this innovation is to streamline timber collection using an online software tool. This tool is specifically designed to improve decision-making by efficiently managing multiple complex variables. These include the locations of cut timber (felling) shown on on-line map (incl. coordinates), status of the felling, the assortment of logs and amount, accessibility and limitations for road traffic, time deadlines for collection, delivery destinations and assortments, trucks available, contact details for communication.

This software is accessible online and caters to various users including multiple dispatchers, drivers, and wood machine operators. It features customisable access controls, allowing specific data visibility and input based on user roles. Additionally, the software supports the generation of different types of reports and can create waybill documents using various pre-designed templates.

Unique feature is possibility to share just part of owners' data e.g. make a reservation for some of timber assortment but leave part of same felling for other dispatcher to collect e.g. with different kind of vehicle (call for help).

For convenience of users, number of filters can be easily applied. A common logic for displaying and adding data is applied throughout the portal.

In the following sections a description of the software is provided:

1.2 Logistics WEB software requirements:

Minimum technical software requirements:

- Operating system: Microsoft Windows 7 or later
Internet browser Mozilla Firefox 47, Google Chrome 51, Microsoft Edge25. Google Chrome is recommended
- Minimum hardware requirements:
- Processor (CPU): Intel i3 or equivalent
- Main memory (RAM): 2GB or more
- Video card: 128MB or more
- Keyboard: ENG/RUS USB or PS/2 or equivalent.
- Minimum technical requirements for the monitor:
- Screen size: 17`
- Resolution: 1024 x 768

1.3 Working with the website

1.3.1 Logging in

- In order to use the system, the user must have created a personal user of the system. If such a user has not been created, please contact the dispatchers of SELF Logistics Ltd. It is strictly forbidden to use other people's user profiles or to give someone your username or password.
- To start the work in the browser you must open the web site (WEB) address <http://kokvedis.selflogistic.lv> (can be changed as software develops)

- in the authorization window you must enter your username and password and press the "Log in" button. Password is case sensitive

SIA Self Loģistika

Kokvedis

1.3.2 Description of each section of the interface

After successful login, the home page opens with the map, various filters and menus (if you have the right to see the map and the relevant sections).

1. Basic map screen

2. Map filter that can filter out the following parameters

- Organisations
- Wood templates
- Cutting status

Options on the left side:

- Map
- Sites
- Operational information
- Classification
- Clients
- Reports

3. Map layer switching (RIGHT panel) and object filter including:

- Google Map
- Google satellite map
- JS map
- JS photo map
- JS topo (topological map)
- Curves
- Delivery points
- All delivery points
- Machines
- Bases

Choice of layer filters
- selection options

- Warehouses
- Prohibition signs
- Info signs

4. LEFT Side menu containing links to all other sections:

- Map - Home screen with map and menus.
- Objects
 - Machines
 - Delivery points
 - Warehouses
 - Stock locations
 - Prohibition signs
 - Info signs
- Operational information
 - Routes
 - Route templates
 - Curbs
 - Waybills
- Classifiers
 - Bermetri (timber volume if put in unorganised way, similar to "cord")
 - Kraujmetri (timber volume if stacked in organised way, but includes spaces)
 - Fuel prices
 - Tariff schedules
 - Coefficients per km

- Coefficients by type of wood
- Wood types
- Wood source types
- Banks
- Bill numbers
- Certificate types
- Customers
 - Transporters
 - Customers
 - Suppliers
 - Logging
- Reports
 - Accompanying notes
 - Logging receipts
 - Waybills for transporter
 - Incoming
 - Circumstances
 - Inventory
 - Roadside inventory
 - Costs by assortment
 - Realisation dynamics
 - ill No. issued
 - Balance of waybill numbers
 - Use of waybill numbers
- Management
 - Organisations

- Entities
- Users
- Assortment templates

5. Side menu hide/show button

6. Current fuel price. Also contains a link to the fuel price classifier where you can add a new fuel price. More details in "Classifiers"

7. User name and username (in brackets):

8. Switch button for the names/circumstance codes. One of 3 possible options to be depicted below the cut point can be selected:

- Felling names
- Felling codes
- Both

9. "Logout" button - to exit the WEB application.

10. Mouse coordinates on the map.

1.3.3 Point icons and text colour explanations

- The icons of the axes are represented by a green circular icon.
Text in light green - Completed removal Text in blue - Tail (small quantities remaining) Text in red - Completed delivery Text in white - Active felling. Text in orange - Unable to approach
- Delivery point icons are represented by a red circular icon.
- Machine icons are represented by a black diamond icon.
- Base icons are represented by a black circular icon.
- Warehouse icons are represented by a yellow circular icon.
- Prohibition signs icons are represented by a black X icon.
- The icons for information signs are represented by a blue hexagonal star icon.

1.3.4 Coordinates correction

To prevent accidental correction of coordinates, by default objects are "locked" and cannot be moved around the map. To correct the coordinates, the object has to be selected and opened in editing mode.

Here are two ways to set the coordinates: Selecting a marker on the map - select point 1 of the image

Manually entering the coordinates - select point 2 of the image

1.3.5 Working with data and filters

A common logic for displaying and adding data is applied throughout the portal.

Kods	Īpašums	Datums no	Statuss
0102-160801	karpas	21.07.2016	Aktīvs
0102-160801-otrā	karpas - otrā	21.07.2016	Aktīvs
10-282	Švarcbahs	21.05.2016	Izvešana pabeigta
11-359	Švarcbahs	02.06.2016	Aizvērts ar datumu
10-672	Siliņš	25.05.2016	Aizvērts ar datumu
10-977	Neilands	06.06.2016	Nevar piebraukt
11-153	Kalniņš	12.04.2016	Nevar piebraukt
11-442	Veinbergs	08.05.2016	Astes

1. Filter - with a filter it is possible to filter the data by certain fields (name, date, etc.).
2. Sort the data by a specific field/column.
3. Leafing function allows to move between result pages.
4. Add data by clicking the "Plus" icon.
5. Edit data by pressing the "Pencil" icon.
6. Results may be displayed in different colours depending on the section in which the data is viewed.

1.3.6 Forest clearings

By default, the map displays all clearcuts that have not been closed by date. The left-hand clearcut filter allows you to filter the clearcuts displayed on the screen by several parameters.

Filtering clearing by organization:

To filter by organisation, remove the tick from the 'All' field of the organisation line and click the mouse cursor in the empty field.

Filtrs ✖

Organizācijas: Visas

|

Koksnes veidnes: Visi

Cirsmas statuss: Visi

select an organisation from the list.

Dynamic filtering is built in - i.e. if you start typing the first letters of an organisation's name, only entries starting with those letters will be filtered out and left.

Selected organisations appear in the list with a grey background, which means that they are already selected. The map automatically filters out the clearings and only shows those where the organisation matches the selected ones.

To remove an organisation from the filter, click on the cross next to the organisation, or select an organisation from the list and click on it again. The already selected organisation will have a grey background.

Filtrs ✖

Organizācijas: Visas

✖ Stracke-Erdman ✖ Konopelski Inc ✖ Ryan Group

Stracke-Erdman

Konopelski Inc

Ryan Group

Blanda, Quitzon and Goyette

Bashirian-Kuphal

1.3.7 Circulation filtering by wood templates

To filter by wood templates, remove the tick from the "All" field of the logging status line and click the mouse cursor in the empty field. Select one of the wood templates.

Dynamic filtering is built in - i.e. if you start typing the first letters of a wood template name, only entries starting with those letters will be filtered out and left.

Selected wood templates appear with a grey background in the list, which means that they are already selected. The map automatically filters out the clearcuts and shows only those where the wood templates match the selected ones. To remove a wood mould from the filter, you need to press on the cross next to the wood mould, or select a wood mould from the list and press on it again. The already selected wood template will have a grey background.

1.3.8 Filtering of felling by felling status

To filter by felling status, remove the tick from the "All" field of the felling status line and click the mouse cursor in the empty field. Select one of the felling statuses.

Dynamic filtering is built in - i.e. if you start typing the first letters of the status name of a logging site, only entries starting with these letters will be filtered out and left.

Selected felling statuses appear in the list with a grey background, which means that they are already selected. The map automatically filters out the clearcuts and shows only those where the clearcut status matches the selected ones.

To remove a logging status from the filter, click on the cross of the five logging statuses, or select a logging status from the list and click on it again. The already selected felling status will have a grey background.

1.3.9 Viewing the felling data

There are 4 ways to view the felling data: by left-clicking once on the selected felling on the map. Right-clicking once on the selected felling on the map. By double-clicking with the left mouse button on the selected felling on the map. By selecting the "Operational Information" section from the left-hand menu, then selecting the " Felling" sub-section.

Left-clicking once on the selected felling site on the map will bring up a blue window showing the current timber data for that particular felling site. The following fields are displayed.

Clicking on the modal window cross or opening a new modal window will close this modal window.

Right-clicking once on the selected harvesting area on the map will pop-up a window showing the current timber data for that particular harvesting area. It is possible to open several of the following pop-up windows. The windows are closed with the cross at the top right of the window.

The window displays the following calculations: Forecast, At the road side, Cut and Delivered to.

Veidne	Pieejams	Kam domāts
BA-LK-A 590 (9-30)	0.00	Gailītis, Ozoliņi and Jurēvics
BA-LK-Os 590 (11-23)	163.60	Kalniņš LLC

The data is displayed in a table with the following fields: Template, cut, delivered to, Reserved (work order created and scheduled to be removed shortly, but no waybill printed yet), available (Calculation from "Delivered minus Removed minus Booked"), for whom.

Double-clicking with the left mouse button on the selected clearing on the map will display a modal window on the right-hand side containing extended information about the clearing. This modal window can be closed with the red cross or with the "Cancel" button.

1.3.10 List of felling sites

In the felling list, felling names and dates are coloured according to the following methodology:

- text in dark green - Closed with date
- text in light green - Withdrawal complete
- text in blue - Tail
- text in red - Withdrawal complete
- text in black - Active felling.
- text in orange - Unable to approach.

1.3.11. Establishing or repairing a new clearing

To create a new coppice, the following must be entered:

- Code (required)
- Name of property (required)
- County (required)
- Parish (required)
- Organisation (required)
- Consignor (required)
- Certificate (required if certificate)
- Supplier (required)
- Season (required)
- Type (required)
- Payment (required)
- Date from (required)
- Date to (optional)
- Completed (optional)

Once this is done, the rest of the felling data in the other sections can be added.

Jauna cirsuma ✖

<p>Kods <input type="text" value="0000777"/></p>	<p>Īpašums <input type="text" value="Jauns cirsmas nosaukums"/></p>
<p>Novads <input type="text" value="Ikšķiles novads"/></p>	<p>Pagasts <input type="text" value="Ikšķiles pilsēta"/></p>
<p>Organizācija <input type="text" value="SELF Loģistika"/></p>	<p>Nosūtītājs <input type="text" value="VER Dižmežs"/></p>
<p>Sertifikāti <input type="text"/></p>	<p>Piegādātājs <input type="text" value="SIA xxx"/></p>
<p>Sezona <input type="text" value="Vissezonas"/></p>	<p>Tips <input type="text" value="Augošs mežs"/></p>
<p>Apmaksa <input type="text" value="Pirms izstrādes"/></p>	
<p>Datums no <input type="text" value="29.07.2016"/></p>	<p>Datums līdz <input type="text"/></p>
<p>Pabeigts <input type="text"/></p>	
<p><input type="button" value="Saglabāt"/> <input type="button" value="Atcelt"/></p>	

1.3.12 Establishment of a new stacking yard

It is possible to add more than one stacker to each cut. To create a new stacker you need to enter:

- Name - stacker name (mandatory)
- Coordinates - coordinates of the stacker which will also be reflected on the map (optional)
- Delivery complete - status that wood delivery is complete (optional)
Branch delivery complete - status that branch delivery is complete (optional)
- Removal complete - This status is set by the controllers when they have removed everything from the clearcut By setting this status, the controllers no longer see the clearcut on the map. (optional)

- "Last driver out" - mark the driver who was the last one to remove the cut. (optional)
- Unable to access - due to various reasons, the loading bay cannot be accessed.(optional)
- Extra - the felling has to be expedited, regardless of the cost (optional)
- Limited control - the most expensive assortment has to be removed urgently. Difficult to control log residues, theft possible (Optional)
- Contractual - logs must be removed by a certain date agreed in the contract (Optional)
- Container - note that the chipper has a container (Optional)
- Notes to driver - notes to driver about the stacker which he will see when he receives the work order. (optional)

70-576 - Kreši - 1					
Prognoze: 59.30			Nocirsts: 105.10		
Pie ceļa: 163.60			Pievests: 163.60		
Veidne	Nocirsts	Pievests	Rezervēts	Pieejams	Kam domāts
BA-LK-Os 590 (11-23)	105.10	163.60	0.00	163.60	Kalniņš LLC
BA-LK-A 590 (9-30)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	Gailītis, Ozoliņi and Jurēvics

Jauna krautuve ✖

Pamatzdati
Krautuves ▾
Informācija ▾
Operācijas ▾

Nosaukums

Koordinātas

[56.98690, 24.49951]
🔒
✎

Pievešana pabeigta

Zaru pievešana pabeigta

"Astes"

Izvešana pabeigta

Pēdējais izveda

Nevar piebraukt

Ekstra

Ierobežota kontrole

Līgumattiecības

Kontainers

Piezīmes šoferim

Saglabāt
Atcelt

For the stockyard mix list, the amounts for the following items are displayed:

Forecast Off Road Cut Delivered

The stockyard mix list is displayed as a table.

The following fields are displayed: template, cut, delivered, reserved.
Available For whom.

Krautuves sortiments ✖

Pamatdati Krautuves ▾ Informācija ▾ Operācijas ▾					
Prognoze: 59.30		Nocirsts: 105.10			
Pie ceļa: 163.60		Pievests: 163.60			
Veidne	Nocirsts	Pievests	Rezervēts	Pieejams	Kam domāts
BA-LK-A 590 (9-30)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	Gailītis, Ozoliņi and Jurēvics
BA-LK-Os 590 (11-23)	105.10	163.60	0.00	163.60	Kalniņš LLC

Krautuves pievestie ✖

Pamatdati Krautuves ▾ Informācija ▾ Operācijas ▾			
Pievienot			
Veidne	Izveidoja	Daudzums	Izveidots
BA-LK-Os 590 (11-23)	admin6	94	20.07.2016 15:11:42
BA-LK-Os 590 (11-23)	rikvaldis108	69.6	20.07.2016 15:11:42

To add arrivals to the stacker, the following must be entered:

- Template
- Quantity

Krautuves pievestie ✖

Pamatdati Krautuves ▾ Informācija ▾ Operācijas ▾

Pievienot

Veidne

- BA-LK-Os 590 (11-23)
- BA-LK-A 590 (9-30)

Saglabāt

Atceļt

Veidne	Izveidoja	Daudzums	Izveidots
BA-LK-Os 590 (11-23)	admin6	94	20.07.2016 15:11:42
BA-LK-Os 590 (11-23)	rikvaldis108	69.6	20.07.2016 15:11:42

The list of access roads to the loading bay is shown in a table.

The following fields are displayed:

- Name
 - Access km. (if greater than zero, indicates that this is an access road)
 - Exit km. (if greater than zero, indicates that this is an exit road)

To add a loading bay access/egress road, you must enter:

- Driveway name
- Router (default JS)
- Routing points (mandatory)

Driveways can be created by double-clicking on the map - thus tilting the map marker. Blue is the base colour. The selected (active) marker is red.

Similarly, for the side route points, the active marker is marked with a red frame.

Jauna krautuves piebrauktuve ✖

Pamatdati
Krautuves ▾
Informācija ▾
Operācijas ▾

Nosaukums

Maršrutētājs:

Piebraukšana: 0.00 km

✕	∞	✎	N57.7242 E25.4686
✕	∞	✎	N57.7230 E25.4675
✕	∞	✎	N57.7222 E25.4694
✕	∞	✎	N57.7204 E25.4759
✕	∞	✎	N57.7199 E25.4785

Izbraukšana: 1.08 km

Saglabāt
Atcelt

Routing is carried out sequentially from the upper route point in the list to the lower route point.

The "object" in this case is the main route point to or from which routing is carried out.

The order of "objects" and waypoints can be changed by shifting them (by holding and dragging with the mouse).

If "Object" is first, it is a departure route.

Please see additional document in a separate file: [Introducing Woodl.pdf](#)

FOREST4EU

Funded by the European Union (Grant n. 101086216). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or REA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

 forest4eu.eu

- FOREST4EU Project
- FOREST4EU Project
- info@forest4eu.eu